

Impact of population growth on forest cover in Tawang District of Arunachal Pradesh, India

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Abstract

The impact of population growth on the forest cover has been much debated worldwide. There is a reciprocal relationship between population growth and forest cover. In other words, population growth turns out to be the main cause of deforestation in many parts of the world. Continued deforestation threatens the well-being and livelihood of millions of people who largely depends on the forest resources. The regions experiencing rapid population growth are reportedly the major areas where deforestation is occurring at alarming rates. Tawang district of Arunachal Pradesh is inhabited by the Monpa tribes who derive their daily requirements like firewood, timber, medicinal plants, food and fodder for their animals from the forest. With the increase in population, the extraction of forest items has also intensified in the recent decades. The firewood extraction appears to be causing maximum impact on forest degradation. The area is characterized by longer winter months so firewood forms the basic source of heating the houses. Every year each household burns at least two fully matured trees to keep their houses warm. The other forms of extraction like timber, food, fodder, medicinal plants, etc. are also contributing in the overall deforestation. Consequently, many important plant species like rhododendron, oak, pine, *taxus* etc. are largely threatened in the area. The paper attempts to examine the population growth trend in the Tawang district and its impact on the forest cover. The study is based on both primary and secondary data sources to analyze the relationship between population growth and forest cover change.

Keywords: Population Growth; Forest Cover; Deforestation; Firewood

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Introduction

The contribution of population growth in altering the face of the earth has a long history. The relation between population dynamics and landscape change was first developed by Thomas Malthus. Malthus (1873) predicted that population growth would lead to famine and an eventual population crash since, he noted, food production tends to increase arithmetically whereas, human populations tend to grow geometrically. The concept of

population change or growth is often used to connote the change in the number of inhabitants of the territory during a specific period of time, irrespective of the fact whether change is negative or positive. The role of population change in deforestation and forest degradation has been much debated. It may make more sense to say that deforestation is a principal ingredient of population growth.

Far from being costly deforestation often pays for itself in fuel, construction material, and timber sales besides providing new land for agriculture (Hartwick, 2005). While population growth and density are unquestionably related to the forest cover trends, there is no simple way to describe or predict that association. The pressure of population growth on the carrying capacity of the environment is also viewed as a major cause of air, water, and solid-waste pollution. The equality of environment is constantly losing its status due to increase in population growth in most countries of the world (John, 1984). The human population grew at unprecedented rate during the last two decades globally. However, population growth changed its form in the twentieth century with the advancement of technology and medical facilities. This has resulted in major demographic transitions, such as changes in rates of births and deaths, age composition and rural population growth rate (Basnyat, 2009). The impact of population changes on forests and the environment is often discussed in terms of biological carrying capacity (i.e.) the maximum number of individuals that a resource can sustain.

However, many factors influence carrying capacity, such as economic development, socio-political processes, trade, technology and consumption preferences. Many studies have reported that demographic changes in conjunction with the other factors have impacted natural resources in general and forests in particular (Outlaw and Engleman, 1999; Hunter, 2000; FAO 2007). Deforestation is one of the major environmental issues from the global perspective which may have destructive or constructive consequences depending upon ecological conditions, extent of economic development and many other factors (Allen, 1983). The degree of international attention to

deforestation is commensurate with the role of forest in the global, national and local ecosystems.

Awareness of the deforestation problem in developing countries emerged in the early 1970's when several studies illustrated the severity of environmental damage and wood shortages attributable to deforestation. These first studies on the subject included graphic descriptions of erosion in mountainous regions and first-hand accounts of desertification in the semi-arid tropics (Daniel and Kulasingan, 1974; Eckholm, 1975, 1976). Today deforestation is occurring at alarmingly rates, especially in the regions that are experiencing rapid population growth. Population pressures are frequently cited as a cause of deforestation. Therefore, an attempt has been made in this paper to understand the trends of population growth and its impact on the forest cover of Tawang district of Arunachal Pradesh (India).

Materials and Methods

Study area

Tawang district of Arunachal Pradesh lies approximately between 91° 30' to 92° 45' East longitudes and 27° 22' to 27° 50' North latitudes. The district shares international boundary with Tibet in the North and Bhutan in the West and South (Fig. 1). The topography of the region is mostly characterized by mountainous and its greater part falls within the higher mountain zone, consisting of snow clad peaks and valleys. Tawang Chu and Nyamjang Chu are the main rivers flowing through the district which flows towards the Bhutan and joins one of the major tributary of Brahmaputra River Manas in Assam. Tawang district is a part of Eastern Himalayas Biodiversity Hotspot. The region is rich in both floral and faunal diversity. On the basis of structural and compositional characteristics, the vegetation of the district is broadly

classified into temperate forest and sub-alpine and alpine forest.

The temperate forests are further classified into broad leaved forest (2750-3000 m) and Temperate coniferous and broad leaved forest (3000-3500 m) while the sub-alpine and alpine forests includes Rhododendron scrub lands (4000-4300 m), Dwarf Rhododendron meadows (4200-4600 m) and High altitude grassy meadows (4350-5250 m). A wide variety of animal species, high mountain birds, mammals, reptiles, snow leopard, Musk deer, barking deer, bear and other animals frolick freely without fear as the Monpa people do not practice hunting and trapping. On an average the areas receives 1653 mm annual rainfall and mean maximum and minimum monthly temperature of 21.66°C and -0.65°C. The average annual relative humidity ranges from 66.21 to 79.35%. Tawang district is inhabited Monpa tribes with a total population of 49,977. The density of population is 23 persons per Sq. km which is higher than the state (Census, 2011). The district is spread over a total area of 2172 sq. km.

Fig. 1. Location of study area in Arunachal Pradesh (India)

Materials and Methods

The study is based on both the primary and secondary sources of data. The primary data was collected through personal interviews and field observations. About 10 villages from Thingbu, Jang, Mukto, Lhou, Kitpi and Dudungkhar circles were selected randomly for the present study. The Gaon Buras (GB), Village elders, Brokpas (transhumant), both the men and women were taken interviews from the selected villages. The Focus Group Discussion (FGD) was adopted to discuss the present condition of forest cover and deforestation rate in the district. Government publications (i.e.) district statistical handbooks of Tawang district (1991-2001 and 2001-2011), Statistical Abstract of Arunachal Pradesh (1991-2001 and 2001-2011) and other published data sources were also used for deriving the trend of population growth. The land use/ land cover maps were prepared from the Satellite Imagery of Indian Remote sensing (IRS) Linear Image Scanning Sensor (LISS) III of two different years (i.e.) 2001 and 2011 to show the change detection by using Integrated Land and Water Information System (ILWIS 3.4) software in Geographical Information System environment.

Fig. 2. Population of Tawang district from 2001 to 2011

Results and Discussion

Impact of Population growth on forest cover: The total population of Tawang district was 38,929 out of which

21846 males and 17078 females as per 2001 Census of India. The population increased to 49,977 with 29,151 male and 20,826 females during the 2011 Census (Fig. 2). The decadal growth rate of the district was 28.37% during the last one decade which is higher than the national average of 17.64% and states average of 26%. The density of population in the district has also increased from 18 persons per sq. km. to 23 persons per sq. km. Such a trend of population growth has intensified the demand for wood, both timber and fuel. The indigenous people use to derive their daily requirements like food, firewood, timber and medicinal plants since many years in sustainable manner. But, the increase in population demands more resources from the forest leading to greater pressure on the available resources. The depletion of forests has several adverse effects to the region with varying intensity from place to place. When forests are destroyed on hillsides, rates of soil erosion typically increase, sometimes dramatically. Faster rates of evaporation in deforested areas can lead to desiccation of soils and potential climatic change. Forests, especially tropical forests, are the home to millions of species whose disappearance depletes the genetic stock available to humans and raises profound ethical concerns (Preston, 1996).

Forest provides a variety of valuable ecological, economic and social services, including; the conservation of biological diversity, carbon storage, soil and water conservation, provision of employment and enhancement of agricultural production system, improvement of urban and peri-urban living conditions (FAO, 1999). More than half of the global fresh water has their source at mountains, supplying all the major rivers as well as many smaller ones and providing critical storage in lakes, glaciers and other places. But the critical role of mountain catchment areas is

threatened by the major land use / land cover changes that take place in mountains and highlands throughout the world. Deforestation and forest degradation are rapid in the mountain areas of developing countries, which often are characterized by rapid population growth and resulting into land scarcity and poverty. Rapid population growth, expansion of cropland, and intensive harvesting of forests for fuelwood and wood exports contribute to deforestation in different areas of the world although the time lags between causes and effects vary dramatically (Allen and Barnes, 1985). The impact of population growth on forest cover in Tawang district has been discussed under the following livelihood activities of people.

Fuelwood

Majority of population in the study area belongs to rural area i.e. about 36,291 (73%) who depends on agriculture, grazing and lumbering as a source of livelihood. Hence, with the increase in rural population density the rate of deforestation also increases. Simultaneously demand for wood, both timber and fuel wood will also arise. Fuel wood gathered from the forested commons is the most important source of domestic energy in the rural areas of many developing countries (Cecelski, Dunkerley and Ramsey, 1979). The fire wood extraction in the district appears to be causing maximum impact on forest degradation as firewood forms the basic source of heating houses in an area which is characterized by longer winter months (Fig. 3). About half of the world's population cooks with biomass fuels, which provide around 35% of energy supplies in the developing countries (World Bank, 1992). But, there is no denying the fact that the other form of extractions are also contributing in deforestation. Earlier, man-nature interaction was quite sustainable when population was very low. But, today due

to increase in population the interaction with forest is intense leading to loss of many important resources. Consequently, many important plant species like

rhododendron, oak, juniper pines and *Taxus baccata* are largely threatened (Nimasow et al., 2016).

Fig. 3. Extraction of firewood in the study area

Fig. 4. Timber extraction activities

Logging

Destructive felling of trees for timber is a means of earning livelihood for the people of rural areas which is another factor responsible for depletion of forest at large. Most of the people who are engaged in logging are ignorant or uneducated leading to extraction of forest resources in unsustainable way. The intensive cultivation is not possible due to less arable land and the people are compelled for logging and timbering to support their family. During the recent decades the timber extraction activities both legal and illegal has multiplied in the area due to population increase and technological developments (Fig. 4). The availability of new saw machines has enabled the people to carry out timber extraction at higher rate.

Grazing

Animal herding and grazing is one of the important occupations to earn livelihood among the local people (Fig. 5). Animals are considered to be as the symbol of wealth in the society. The Brokpas and Yengtepas are the people who are engaged in animal rearing. These people migrate from one place to another with their herds in search of pasture land and fodder for their herds. While doing so, they set fires on the forest and convert them into grazing land which is one of the causes of forest degradation. With the growing population such cases of forest destruction are frequently reported from the area. Desertification has been widely identified as a major human-induced global change associated with excessive pressure on grasslands (Meyer and Turner, 1992; Nimasow et al., 2016).

Agriculture

Farming is by far the most important human activity that has transformed the land, and continues to be the principal route by which humans affect the environment. Eleven percent of the earth's land surface is now cultivated,

although less than one percent is in permanent crop (Waggoner, 1994). Introduction of new agricultural practices (i.e.) apple, kiwi and orange cultivation in some parts of the area with suitable climatic conditions have came up in the recent years. Large scale clearance of forests for such kind of commercial cultivation has also contributed in the forest cover loss. Though, economic necessity is the driving force behind this change but the role of population growth in creating the demand for this kind of products cannot be undermined.

Developmental activities

In the recent times numbers of unplanned developmental activities are coming up in the district like mini hydro electricity projects and dams. Most of the small streams are designated for Mini Hydro electricity projects. At present, there are more than 87 mini hydro projects and three micro hydro projects which have largely contributed in forest cover loss. Such developmental activities have polluted the streams and resulted into loss of biodiversity. These unplanned projects have led to the destruction of forest.

Land Use / Land Cover (2001-2011)

The total area under forest cover of the study area was 47.71% of out of the total geographical area in the year 2001 (Fig. 6 & Table 1). However, this percentage has come down to 29.08% during the year 2011, which is a change of 18.63% (Fig. 7). This change may be attributed to various human activities like firewood extraction, logging, grazing, agriculture, developmental activities etc. The percentage of total area under agriculture has decreased from 6.30% during 2001 to 5.32% during the year 2011. This result points towards the peoples shift from agricultural activities towards other activities like government services and logging which gives higher

Fig. 5. Conversion of forest into grasslands

Fig. 6. Land use /Land cover map of Tawang district 2001

Table 1. Land use/ Land cover of Tawang (2001 and 2011)

Land Use / Land Cover	Category	Area in %	
		2001	2011
	Agriculture	6.30	5.32
	Settlement	4.09	9.49
	Deciduous Forest	19.34	6.08
	Temperate forest	11.10	9.00
	Alpine Forest	17.27	14.00
	Alpine Grass land /Degraded Forest	8.15	18.71
	Barren surface	13.75	22.11
	Snow Cover	14.73	4.45
	Water body	0.42	7.68
	Shadow	4.84	2.86
	Total	100	100

Fig. 7. Land use /Land cover map of Tawang district 2011

return. The settlements have more than doubled during the last 10 years. The area under settlements was 4.09% in 2001 which became 9.49% in 2011. It clearly reveals that the increasing pressure of population on forest resources is increasing.

There is a decrease of 13.26% in case of deciduous forest in the district. It was 19.34% in the year 2001 which became 6.08% in the year 2011. This category of forest is mainly known for fire woods among the Monpas of

Tawang district because some of the best quality of fire wood (i.e.) Oaks are found in this category. The temperate and alpine forest has also declined from 11.10% in 2001 to 9.00% in 2011 and 17.27% during 2001 to 14.00% during 2011 respectively. The reason for the downward trend of these forest types could be attributed to logging practices and increasing family size of the transhumant and other human activities. Likewise, the barren surface which was 13.75% during 2001 has almost doubled to reach 22.11%

in 2011. In the year 2001, about 14.73% of the land was covered by snow but in the year 2011 it has declined to only 4.45%. Due to the receding snow the percentage of water bodies increased from 0.42% in 2001 to 7.68% during 2011. On the other hand, the percentage of alpine grass land or degraded forest has increased from 8.15% in the year 2001 to 18.71% in 2011. The analysis of population growth and land use / land cover of the study area reveals that during the last decade there is a positive correlation between the population growth and the forest cover change. The population density of the area was 18 persons per sq. km. in the year 2001 with a forest cover of 47.71% out of the total area. With the increase in population density to 23 persons per sq. km. in the year 2011 the forest cover has drastically declined to 29.08% out of the total area. Hence, with the present rate of population growth the forest cover of the area would be largely affected in the coming years.

Conclusion

The study area has a population density of 23 persons per sq. km with a decadal growth rate of 25.92%. Although, the figure appears small but keeping in view the nature of terrain, climatic constraints and resource limitations such a growth rate of population is likely to cause unprecedented results in future. Firewood seems to be one of the important factors behind the increasing rate of deforestation, because it is the only cheap and easily available energy sources to keep their houses warm as other forms of energy are limited. Intensive cultivation is not possible due to less arable land and people are compelled for livestock rearing and grazing which is a threat to the forest cover as people convert forest areas into grazing lands through forest fire. Some section of the people are engaged in logging practices as they have no

other options to earn their livelihood which also contributes a lot in the forest cover loss. The impact of growing demands of commercial agriculture such as Apple, kiwi and orange in the region cannot be ruled out. Awareness of the people through community participation by the Government policies and programs and NGOs could play significant role in sustainable extraction of forest resources. Alternative energy sources like solar and hydro electricity as a substitute to firewood in cooking and heating purposes can reduce the pressure on forest resources. Government assistance in form of financial, fodder, medication etc. to the Brokpa (semi-nomadic people) community may reduce the conversion of forest land into grazing land.

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